

CREATING WRITING AND SPEAKING ACTIVITIES WITH NEWSPAPERS

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Annotation: *The following article is named “Creating listening and speaking activities with newspapers” which includes effective teaching methods in English language courses. This work is devoted to make English lessons more effective and productive . Important topics and suggestions on the subject have been presented.*

Key words: *Writing, speaking, newspaper, brochures, genres.*

English language students discover a whole new world through newspapers, new words, new phrases, new ideas and even new faces! They may have read the news in their own language but reading it in English is so much more exciting and puts the English language in to context for them.

Students love being able to understand and read current news in English and there is something to interest everyone in a newspaper.

Newspapers and magazines: the different kinds of text found in newspapers and magazines offer a range of possibilities for **genre analysis**, followed by writing within that genre. For example, we can get students to look at a range of different articles and ask them to analyze how headlines are constructed, and how articles are normally arranged (e.g. the first paragraph often- but not always- offers a summary of the whole article). They then write an article about a real or imaginary news story that interests them. At advanced levels, we can get students to look at the same story dealt with by different kinds of publications and ask them to write specifically for one or the other.

We can do the same kind of genre analysis in newspaper and magazine advertisements. ‘Lonely hearts’ entries, for example, always conform to a genre frame. Our students can learn a lot of from analyzing the genre and the being able to imitate it. In the same vein, agony column letters (where people write in to ask for help with a problem) offer engaging writing practice.

Finally, we can show students a story and have them respond to it in a variety of different genres, and for different audience (e.g. the report of a long traffic delay can prompt letters to the newspaper, emails, text messages, letters of apology, etc.).

Brochures and guides: we can get students to look at a variety of brochures (e.g. for a town, entertainment venue, health club or leisure complex) to analyses how they are put together. They can then write their own brochure or town guide, using this analysis to help them.

Younger learners may enjoy writing brochures and guides for their areas which give completely wrong information (e.g. ‘Sending postcards home: Look for the bins

marked “Rubbish” or “Litter” and your postcards will be delivered next day; Travelling by bus: The buses in London are similar to taxis. Tell the drivers where you want to go and they’ll drive you home!’). This is potentially just as engaging for children and teenagers as writing serious piece of work.

Poetry: many teachers like getting students to write poems because it allows them to express themselves in a way that other genres, perhaps, do not. But we will have to give students models to help them write (to start with, anyway), since many of them will be unused to this kind of writing.

We can ask them to write acrostic poems (where the letters which start each line, when read downstairs, form a word which is the topic of the poem). They can write a poetry alphabet (a line for each letter), or we can give them sentence frames to write with ‘I like ... because ...’ x 3, and then ‘But I hate ...’). We can get them to write lines about someone they like with instructions such as ‘Write about this person as if they were a kind of weather’. We can give them models of real poems which they have to imitate.

Poetry writing is especially appropriate for younger learners who are usually not afraid to have a go in the ways suggested above; but it is appropriate for older learners, too, since it allows them to be more creative than is permitted in some other activities.

Collaborative writing: students gain a lot from constructing text together.

For example, we can have them build up a letter on the board, where each line is written by a different student (with help from the class, the group and/or the teacher). We can tell a story which students then have to try to reproduce in groups (a version of this activity goes by the name dictogloss, where, when students have tried to recreate what they have heard, they compare their versions with the original as a way of increasing their language awareness).

We can set up a **story circle** in which each student in the group has a piece of paper on which they write the first line of a story (which we dictate to them). They then have to write the next sentence. After that, they pass their papers to the person next to them, and they write the next sentence of the story they now have in front of them. They then pass the paper to the next student and again write the next sentence of the (new) story they have. Finally, when the papers get back to their original owners, those students write the conclusion.

Students can also engage in collaborative writing around a computer screen.

Writing to each other: the email interview is an example of getting students to write to each other. They can also write emails, or any other kind of message (the teacher can act as a postal worker) which has to be answered. They can be involved, under our supervision, in live chat sessions on the Internet, or we can organize **pen pal** exchanges with students in other countries (often called mousepals or keypals when done via the Internet).

Writing in other genres: there are countless different genres that students can write in apart from those mentioned so far. We can have students write personal **narratives** and other stories. We can prepare them for this by looking at the way other

writers do it. We can analyze first lines of novels and then have students write their own attention-grabbing lines. We can get students to complete stories that are only half told. For many of these activities, getting the students to think together before they attempt the task-**brainstorming** ideas- will be a major factor in their success.

Students can write discursive essays in which they assemble arguments both **for and against** a proposition, work out a coherent order for their arguments, study various models for such an essay and then write their own. The procedures we follow may be similar to the spoken discussion ideas.

All these ideas depend for their success on students having a chance to share ideas, look at examples of the genre, plan their writing and then draft and edit it.

Correcting written work.

Most students find it very dispiriting if they get a piece of written work back and it is covered in red ink, underlinings and crossings-out. It is a powerful visual statement of a fact that their written English is terrible.

Of course, some pieces of written work are completely full of mistakes, but even in these cases, over-correction can have a very demotivating effect. Rather than this, the teacher has to achieve a balance between being accurate and truthful, on the one hand, and treating students sensitively and sympathetically, on the other.

2.2 Practical techniques.

One way of avoiding the 'over-correction' problem is for teachers to tell their students that for a particular piece of work they are only going to correct mistakes of punctuation, or only spelling or only grammar, etc. This has two advantages: it makes students concentrate on that particular aspect, and it cuts down on the **correction**.

Another technique which many teachers use is to agree on a list of written symbols (S=spelling, WO= word order, etc.). When they come across a mistake, they underline it discreetly and write the symbol in the margin. This makes correction look less damaging. Where students write with electronic media, teachers can use editing tools such as Track Changes. These make it easier for students to write correct versions of their originals. However, such applications should be used carefully since they, too, can be very discouraging.

The way we react to students' writing will depend on what kind of writing it is. When students hand us final piece of work, we may correct it using techniques such as the ones above. However, while students are actually involved in the writing process, correction will not help them learn to edit their own work, whereas **responding** (telling students what you think, teasing out alternatives and making suggestions) will. But whatever kind of writing students have been doing, we need to react not just to the form of what they have written, but also to the content (what they have written about). We also need to make sure that students do not just put corrected work into their folders without fully understanding why we have reacted as we have, and without doing their best to put things right.

Handwriting.

Now that so much writing is done with electronic media, it may seem perverse to

worry about handwriting. Nevertheless, many people around the world still write with pens and pencils, and so we will need to help any students who have problems of legibility.

Many nationalities do not use the same kind of script as English, so for students from those cultures, writing in English is doubly difficult: they are fighting to express themselves at the same time as trying (when they are not using a computer keyboard) to work out a completely new writing system.

Teachers cannot ask students to change their handwriting style, but they can encourage neatness and legibility. Especially when students are intending to take pen-and-paper exams, such things are crucial. Special classes or group sessions may have to be arranged to help students who are having problems with English script. They can be shown examples of certain letters, and the teacher can demonstrate the strokes necessary for making those shapes. They may also need to be shown where to start the first stroke of a letter as writing from left to right is difficult for some students. They can be asked to write in the air to give them confidence or to trace letters on lined paper which demonstrates the position and height of letters, before going on to imitate them.

CONCLUSION

For as long as people have been learning and teaching languages, there has been continual debate about how to describe the process and what the best ways of doing it are. Much current teaching practice is the direct result of such constructive argument.

Communicative language teaching has two main strands: the first is that language is not just bits of grammar, it also involves language functions such as inviting, agreeing and disagreeing, suggesting etc., which students should learn how to use. They also need to be aware of the need for approaches when talking and writing to people in terms of the kind of language they use (formal, informal, tentative, technical etc.)

The second strand of communicative language teaching developed from the idea that if students get enough exposure to language and opportunities for its use-and if they are motivated- then language learning will take care of itself. In other words, the focus of much communicative language teaching became what we have called Activation, and study tended to be downplayed to some extent.

Communicative Language Teaching has had a thoroughly beneficial effect since it reminded teachers that people learn languages not so that they “know” them, but so that they can communicate. Giving students different kinds of language, pointing them to aspects of style and approaches, and above all giving them opportunities to try out real language within the classroom humanized what had sometimes been too reinserted. Above all, it stressed the need for Activation and allowed us to consider elicitation, extended brainstorming and patchwork-type lessons where before they tended to be less widely used.

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